

Research

An Investigating Effectiveness of Class Room Based for Improving Academic Writing of Undergraduate Students at Shaheed Benazir Bhutto University Shaheed Benazirabad

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Abstract: *Class room based assessment is a basic tool to assess students learning process. CBA is important method of assessment to get quick response from students. It helps to improve students reading, communicative and writing skills. CBA is effective technique to assess student's performance in class room. Classroom based assessment is an outgoing process to judge students' progress. In class room based assessment teachers and students both involve for teaching and learning process. Teachers make students attention in class room to make effective teaching and learning process. This study investigates effectiveness of class room based assessment for students writing skills. Class room based assessment is teacher's input and student's output process. CBA helps teachers to see the weaknesses of students within class room for their writing skills. Classroom based assessment helps student to learn new techniques analyze their deficiencies and writing skills. In this research qualitative method is used to collect data .Mostly twenty five students are selected. Participants are randomly selected for survey. Semi-structured interviews are conducted from teachers in Department of English SBBU-SBA and students from Department of English and Information Technology. Open ended question are designed for interview. Data is collected through recording and transcription. The findings of this research demonstrated that mostly all students and teachers were satisfied with class room based assessment for their teaching and learning process.*

Introduction

Assessment refers to the process by which teachers record the performance of students. It is a tool to know about effectiveness of teachers' teaching and improvement in learning. Effective assessment plays vital role in education in order to classify the level of students and it helps them to go ahead with sequential procedures. Assessment is not only conducted for students, in the same way it is an assessment of teacher as well as institute. Formative assessment has the possibility to help both teachers and students regulate teaching and teach (Fisher & Frey, 2007). Most of the teachers do not utilize formative assessment data to inform future instruction. In a survey given by Edman et al., teachers described that they know that formative assessment is an important practice, but the implementation of the practice is sometimes difficult. Additionally, Volante and Beckett (2011) found that many teachers conveyed tensions in using approaches such as peer assessment and self-assessment.

Teachers described that students' lack of objectivity and mastery of the content was at the centre of this tension. Furthermore, Gates (2008) revealed no statistically significant differences between teachers by grade level, content area, or years of teaching experience in the use, preparedness, and confidence of assessment techniques. Formative assessment has been significantly employed in almost all reformed educationists countries. One of the reasons behind its significance is that it occurs during teaching and employed to progress not to merely grade (Earl 2003). Therefore, formative assessment is considered as a positive and constructive phenomenon. Both formative and summative assessments have prose and cones. Meanwhile, policy makers consider summative more formal and authentic. Since formative assessment is treated less judgmental. Speaking and writing, mainly, have high importance in enhancing EFL level of proficiency. Particularly, speaking has been always taken as primary means of communication while writing took as secondary means of communication. As a matter of fact, by time we came to realize the importance of writing precisely an integral part of learners' language development and the role of the teacher as the core of enhancing the writing skills while adopting various approaches and techniques in order to understand all students' needs and difficulties. Consequently, as an effective procedure,

teachers realize the importance of classroom assessment as an effective technique in getting their goals while teaching writing skills.

Background of research

Assessment is a process of critical analyses for teacher in which he observes important parameters of teaching and learning in classroom. It is a complex process because there is no any producer to accomplish it. Nor it is the business of accidental teachers. Assessment is a boring and time taking activity and only dedication is demanded to function it. Researcher is talking about the condition of Pakistani education system generally and talking about Sindh province which is at last number among its entire provinces in quality education particularly. Assessment demands pure consciousness and impartiality. This study is conducted in order to investigate the ongoing practices for taking classroom-based assessment. It takes only Shaheed Benazir Bhutto University, Shaheed Benazirabad.

Statement of the problem

Classroom based assessment is the teachers' everyday input as well as students' everyday output. Teachers' classroom assessment seeks to provide positive feedback to the students as a key component to writing skills and to overcome their deficiencies. For students, the writing task represents the main difficulty, according to them writing needs further practice and techniques to follow in order to master. Therefore, In EFL classrooms, teachers should call students' attention to their formative comments and feedback on their writing progress; in order, to improve their writing and to be aware of their own writing deficiencies. Thus, throughout this study researcher tends to highlight the importance of classroom assessment on students' progress, putting much emphasis on its role in enhancing students' writing proficiency. Also, this study would aim to show teachers' role in developing students writing skill through adopting different writing approaches and strategies by which students will respond and react effectively.

Objectives of the study

This study investigates the role of classroom-based assessment for improving university students' academic writing. There are three main objectives based on problem statements.

- To investigate the techniques to conduct classroom-based assessment in academic writing class.
- To investigate the effectiveness of classroom-based assessment for improving academic writing skills.
- To investigate perceptions of teachers and students towards classroom-based assessment in improvement of academic writing.

Literature Review

Classroom Assessment is one of significant area of study and comprises many critical dimensions of study. Researchers' focus is increased in classroom investigation due to its direct impacts on teaching and learning process in educational institutes. Few of important contributions are discussed below in detailed. An effective study in (Zhao, Van den Heuvel-Panhuizen, & Veldhuis, 2016) presented to investigate class room learning objective by teaching mathematics. However, female's teachers were selected in their study for delivering lecture objective in class-room. The data collection methods in their approach have been used from interview, forms, lesson observations and final class report. Their study found that a teacher can implement CATs in class room in effective way adopting new trends and can improve class student cognitive learning. Most of teachers respond was positive towards CATs. However it may improve performance and satisfaction level of both students as well as teacher. Another study in (Yang & Mak, 2017) fuzzy comprehension evaluation method (FCE) of class room. In their study author focused on class room acoustical environment. Five important factors are considered to collect data from questionnaire. This is a useful and effective assessment model proposed by the author for class room monitoring.

Many critical parameters can be investigate furthermore in class room learning environment related to both teacher as well as students as in (Mah Abosalem & Abosalem, 2016) focused on techniques of class room assessment in their study. Teaching evaluation methods are important for investigating critical factors for young learners. Author in (Rincon-Flores, Gallardo, & Fuente, 2018) discussed gamification approach in learning process by applying computerised methods of

assessment in class room. Three types of data has been considered in their study for analysis of student learning improvement. To assess students creative learning is not an easy task for teacher which is focused in study (Ahmadi, Peter, Lubart, & Besançon, 2019). Author has focused on environmental factors in school which improves student's creative skills and on same place these skills can also be degraded if not proper learning environment is provided. The study encountered creative and self-assessed methods of learning. The strength of class is very important for effective learning consideration for students. Individual assessment has been good practice in classroom since centuries. The study by (Obradović, Sulik, Finch, & Tirado-Strayer, 2018) introduced an novel approach of group assessment in class room. Group assessment can save time and help teacher to observe students critically and comparatively. A comprehensive survey study has been presented in (Rahmat et al., 2019). In this study author has selected 48 physical education teachers randomly from 15 different institutes and designed questionnaire for data collection for student physical assessment and learning.

Auerbach (2018) stated that though active-learning instruction had the potential to positively impact the preparation and diversity of STEM graduates, not all instructors were able to achieve this potential. Author investigated the pedagogical knowledge that 77 instructors who reported implementing active-learning instruction used as they analyzed video clips of lessons in large active-learning biology courses. The author used qualitative content analysis, and drew on cognitive and socio-cultural perspectives of learning, to identify and characterize the pedagogical knowledge instructors employed.

Durlak (2011) presented findings from a meta-analysis of 213 school-based, universal social and emotional learning (SEL) programs involving 270,034 kindergartens through high school students. The use of 4 recommended practices for developing skills and the presence of implementation problems moderated program outcomes. The findings add to the growing empirical evidence regarding the positive impact of SEL programs. James and Tayyaba (2015) described that in UK medical schools, five-option single-best answer (SBA) questions were the most widely accepted format of summative knowledge assessment. However, writing SBA questions with four effective incorrect options was difficult and time consuming, and consequently, many SBAs contained high frequency of implausible distracters. The study investigated the frequency of non-functioning distracters in a sample of 480 summative SBA questions at Cardiff University. A survey

questionnaire was additionally administered to 108 students (33 % response rate) to gain insight into their perceptions of these models. The questionnaire survey revealed that the student body had mixed views towards the proposed format change. This study was one of the first to comprehensively investigate distracter performance in SBA examinations in undergraduate medical education. It provided evidence to suggest that using three-option SBA questions would maximise efficiency whilst maintaining, or possibly improving, psychometric quality, through allowing a greater number of questions per exam paper.

William (2014) has discussed the following seven issues affecting assessment of undergraduates in universities: decision making and the selection of tests, the use of written and oral assignments to measure learning, the characteristics of grades and portfolios for evaluating students, opportunities for self-assessment and feedback to instructors, retention of learning and the testing for higher ordered thinking, the psychology of students in the economics classroom, and the development of new tests as public goods. Olivares-Donoso (2019) demonstrated that over the last 25 years, both research literature and practice-oriented reports had claimed the need for improving the quality of undergraduate science education through linking research and teaching. In this article, we present a literature review aimed at synthesizing and comparing results of the impact of participating in these research experiences to establish which approach was most beneficial for students to develop as scientists. Rustam et al. (2017) stated in their study that the effectiveness of the application of speech-to-text recognition (STR) technology on enhancing learning and concentration in a calm state of mind, hereafter referred to as meditation (An intentional and self-regulated focusing of attention in order to relax and calm the mind), was investigated.

Materials and methods

This study employed a qualitative case study approach with multiple participants (Creswell, 2013). Because this study sought to explore male and female teachers' experiences of teaching reading in Shaheed Benazir Bhutto University, Shaheed Benazirabad, Pakistan. A qualitative approach was appropriate to answer the research questions; collecting data directly from the participants' daily experiences. Creswell and Poth (2013) have stated that "qualitative researchers study things in their natural settings, attempting to make sense of, or interpret, phenomena in terms of the meaning people bring to them". Qualitative research seeks to better understand a problem or issue from participants' personal experiences. The case study was conducted in two different departments

of Shaheed Benazir Bhutto University, Shaheed Benazirabad, Pakistan, namely Department of English, Department of Information Technology with five teachers participants' one female and four male teachers and twenty students from both departments, all of whom were writing based teachers at the university. In sum, the study was based upon the daily experiences of 4 male and one female teachers and four male who taught writing skills inside the classroom in Shaheed Benazir Bhutto University, Shaheed Benazirabad, Pakistan.

Results and Discussion:

Data Collection

Data collection is systematic way to get responses on the matter. A range of instruments can be used to get samplings for exploring the phenomenon. Among a number of different kinds of interviews, this study used semi-structured interviews because it gives freedom to participants to explain the phenomena in their own way. The most useful interview format for conducting qualitative research is often “semi-structured” (sometimes called “moderately scheduled”). This means the interview is not highly structured, as is the case of an interview that consists of all closed-ended questions, nor is it unstructured, such that the interviewee is simply given a license to talk freely about whatever comes up.

Participants and Sampling

This study collected data from five university senior teachers were selected for semi-structured interviews. All teachers belong to same Department of English. Students were randomly selected. First, researchers get consent from Dean Faculty of Social Sciences and explained about the objectives of research. Then, researcher visited the Shaheed Benazir Bhutto University, Shaheed Benazirabad and meet with the Chairman Department of English. After meeting with Chairman, researcher selected five senior teachers for the semi-structured interview. The researcher kept all interviews recorded and further transcribed them impartially.

Semi structured Interviews

The interview questions were carefully constructed according to the theme of research. Following questions are given separately for teachers and students. Interview Questions for students are:

- 1 What are the techniques of English language teachers to conduct classroom-based assessment in academic writing class?
- 2 How far is classroom-based assessment effective for improving academic writing?
- 3 What are the perceptions of university students and teachers towards Classroom Based Assessment?
- 4 What are the techniques of English language teachers to conduct classroom-based assessment in academic writing class?
- 5 How far is classroom-based assessment effective for improving academic writing?
- 6 What are the perceptions of university students and teachers towards Classroom Based Assessment?
- 7 Does summative assessment have advantage for students?
- 8 What techniques of assessment do you think are beneficial for academic writing skills?

Interview questions for teachers are:

1. What can be done further to improve academic writing skills?
2. What can be done further to improve academic writing skills?
3. What do you know about classroom-based assessment?
4. Which assessment do you prefer to improve your waiting skills?
5. What role teacher can play to improve your academic writing skills?
6. What techniques do you think are beneficial for academic writing?
7. How teacher give you feedback in the classroom?
8. How do you feel while teacher give you feedback in the classroom?
9. What techniques do you prefer to improve your academic writing skills?
10. What further can be done to improve your academic writing skills?

Result and Discussion

Background Information of the Teachers.

Table No # the interviews teachers Statistics

PI	DGN	UNI	TN	GNR	QLF	TE	AG
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Participants	Lecturer	SBBU	05	Male	MS in AL: 03	3-4 YEARS	29-35 Years
				04	BS in AL: 01	1-2 YEARS	old
Participants	Lecturer			Female	MS in AL: 01	1 Years	28 Years old
				01	BS in AL: 00	2-3 years	0

Note: Participants identification, DGN: Designation, TN: total number, UNI: University, GNR: Gender, QLF: Qualification, TE: teaching experience, AG: Age

In Table 4.1 total teachers were five among them four were male and one was female. Two were MS in English linguistics two were MS in English literature while one was BS in English. Lecturers who were MS in English linguistics they have 6 to 7 year of teaching experience and other two who were MS in English literature had 5 to 6 year of teaching experience had two year teaching experience while who was BS in English had only 1 to 2 year of teaching experience of English at SBBU,SBA.

Assessment through Speaking

Assessment through speaking is the first most important main theme of this study. Almost all student participants as well as teacher participants agreed that assessment through speaking is the most important for developing students' abilities. However five students explained that teachers can assess students' knowledge and interest through speaking. They reported:

“.....speaking can enhance my capabilities and our teachers assess us when I deal my classroom presentation.....” [Student Informant One]

Three of the teachers narrated:

T 3: “Oh yes through speaking we can assess mistakes of students very quickly an easily through speaking. If we check mistake during speaking then they will to make those mistakes in writing as well”.

T 4: “I think so it is best way to judge mistakes of students through speaking. Speakings helps students to decrease their mistakes

T 5:”.....Hmmm really it is useful tool for checking mistakes of students. Speaking is a major tool to improve writing skills of students”.

Two of the teachers opposed and said:

T 1: Ah As we know most of the students have no ability to understand language of teachers. Or some students avoid speak before other students so in my view it will not be fruitful for students academic writing skills.

T 2: “Definitely there are various types of students who have their own level of understanding. So speaking can also make hindrances some of the students because if they are not able to talk or if they are not able to understand teacher’s language, then definitely they cannot improve their academic writing”.

Assessment through Writing

Assessment through writing is the main second theme of this research. Mostly all students as well as teachers were satisfied with it that through writing students builds up their abilities of writing skills. However, some teachers described that it is one of the most effective factor for writing skills of the students. One of them reported that

“ah yes assessment through writing is the best way to see the or check the proper mistakes of the students.

Four of the students said:

S 5: “ah.... actually in my view that we learn a lot through writing. Really through writing process our teachers assesses our writing and then points out our mistakes and we improve our writing”.

S 3: “Of course assessing through writing is the best way for assessing our mistakes.

S 6: “It is better for us to learn assessing through writing. Through writing we can improve our mistakes.

S 2: I like writing skills better for improving writing skills.

One of the students opposed and said:

“I think writing process is very difficult. Some of the students are weak in writing and cannot write and also try to avoid writing. So if students are not involved in writing then how they can improve their writing. So in my opinion it is one the difficult problem for improving writing”.

Assessment through Listening

Assessment through listening is the third main theme of this study. Most of the students and teachers agreed that listening is the best way for students developing abilities. Listening is the good way for enhancing abilities of students. One of the teachers said that:

“.....of course assessment through listening is an important factor for improving writing skills of students”

Two of the students said:

S 1: “Assessing through listening is more important for us to improve our grammatical mistakes”

S 2: “Yes it is helpful for our writing skills through listening also we can improve our writing skills”.

4.4.1 Error correction

Error correction is also one of the major themes of this study. Most teachers as well as students agreed that through error correction students get good developing abilities for writing. Mostly teachers agreed through error correction we judge our students mistakes and correct them. One teacher reported that:

“Error correction is main and important way to observe the check and balance about the mistakes of students”

4.4.2 Feed backs

Feedback is the fifth theme of this study. Mostly participants as well as teachers agreed that feedback is the major component for improving students' abilities. Feedback plays vital role for students' achievements in writing skills. One of the students said:

“.....feedback is more important way of understanding and judging the mistakes of students

Assessment Through Activities

Assessment through different activities is the major theme of this study. Most of the students and teachers views are that through making different activities in the class room students can make their writing skills better. This is the most fruitful way for student's progress. Two teachers reported:

“...we assessed students through different classroom activities”.

“Some of my students do not take part in classroom activities....activities can be the tool for assessment of our students' knowledge....”

However, one student participant asserted:

“My teachers mostly do not give back our tasks; so we cannot check or see our mistakes....and we are unable to improve....”

4.5.1 Improving grammar skills

Improving grammar skills is the second theme of this study. It is the way through which students try to overcome their grammatical mistakes. Mostly all the teachers and students are agreed that through improving grammar skills students can improve their abilities of writing skills. Three of these participants said:

T1: “...grammar is very important to develop our abilities”.

T4: “Grammar enables students to write correctly any piece of composition”.

T5: “Students can speak and write correctly if they know about grammar”.

Conversely, one student opposed the knowledge of grammars and said:

“I do not think grammar is important for speaking. I speak without grammar but it is useful for writing”

4.5.2 Improving sentence structure

This is the third theme of this research. It is one of the main beneficial factor through which students make proper sentence structure and try to reduce their mistakes. Mostly all participants’ boys and girls are agreed that this is the best way for overcome writing skills.

Five of the students narrated

S 3: “of course through sentence structure our language become better and make our sentence correct slowly”

S 7: “No doubt sentence structure is very much important for our mistakes if learn sentence structure then we can improve our writing skills”.

S 9: “I think sentence structure is good and beneficial for our writing”. It helps us to make our sentence correct and slowly and gradually we learn more and reduces our mistakes”.

S 12: “I think so it is essential to learn sentence structure for improving writing skills.

S 16: “It is better for us to get knowledge about grammar and sentence structure because it is best way to make our writing better”.

Two of the students opposed this and said

S 19: “I think some of the students among us have no interest in grammar and sentence structure. So they avoid grammar and sentence structure and do not focus on writing skills.

S 17: “So in my view grammar and sentence structure is boring. So I do not take interest in sentence structure or rules and regulation.

Section two the interviews and the results of the teacher’s perception about the CBA.

Table No # 02 Results of interview of second Question

Which assessment do you prefer to improve academic writing of the students?
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Theme / Node	Case	Percentage	References / Cases Response
Grammar Error	T1 and T2	40	Sentence Structure, tenses and spelling.
Quick Feedback	T5 and T3	40	Helps to get fast feedback
Pronunciation	T4	20	Words accent, pronunciation and fluency

Question 1. What do you know about classroom-based Assessment?

T1: Classroom-based assessment is such kind of assessment in which the teacher is taking or assessing of the students and their performance and protection during the class.

T2: Yes, I know that there are two types of assessment, one is summative assessment and second one is formative assessment now as for summative assessment is concerned that is conducted after that you can say year after semester. So that is not useful for the classroom so surely exactly formative assessment is fruitful

T3: Well class room based assessment is most of the time what we do the students we conduct some different type of activities writing activities, listening activities, speaking activities and through these activities we judge our students we assessed our students as for as their mistakes are concerned, and as for as you know problems are concerned during their grammar skills as for as structure is concerned there are lot of problems when they are writing different sentences or when they speak some sentence so during classroom we assess them and we also give them their solution to solve their problems.

T4: Classroom-based Assessment is assessment which in teachers is observing the students with in the class room.

T5: Classroom-based assessment is assessment in which teachers observes student's performance and ability during the classroom.

Question: 2 which assessments do you prefer to improve academic writing skills of the students?

TI: Mostly, I use classroom-based assessment. I always assess my students after delivering my lecture within the classroom. It is helpful for the student because student make grammatical

mistake and teacher observe grammatical mistakes of the student within the classroom and suggest them how to remove mistakes and how to improve writing skills.

T2: That is, I would prefer formative assessment because this improves the writing skills of the students because this is the assessment which can give benefit advantage to the students directly. In which teachers observes spelling mistakes within the classroom.

T3: In my opinion classroom-based assessment is the best tool for improving academic writing skills of the students. It helps students to get feedback within the classroom and then students' day by day improves writing skills.

T4: I think so the formative assessment is suitable for improving the academic writing skills of the students because during the class check and balance would be there and it would be good assessment was there so that I think every teacher should suggest and advice and to give preference and priority to formative assessment.

T5: There should be a formative because in this assessment teacher tries to find out grammatical mistakes of the students within the classroom. So, students can get easier response.

In table 4.7 results shows that 40 percent theme coverage T5 and T3 indicate that classroom-based assessment helps teacher in getting quicker and easier feedback 40 percentage theme coverage of T1 and T2 indicate that classroom-based assessment helps teacher to improve grammatical mistakes of the students. 20 percent average T4 indicates that CBA helps teacher to improve also proper pronunciation of the words.

4.6 SECTION-2: The Interviews and Result of the students Perceptions about CBA

Table No # the interviews Students Statistics

PI	DGN	UNI	TN	GNR	QLF
Participants	Students	SBBU	05	Male	MA ENG : 07
				13	BS in ENG: 06
Participants	Students	SBBU	05	Female	MA in ENG: 04
				07	BS in ENG: 03

Which assessment do you prefer to improve academic writing skills?

S1: I like formative assessment it is good for getting feedback within the class

S2: Mostly, I like classroom-based assessment, it is assent in which teacher assess students spelling word structure sentence striker with the class.

S3: in my idea classroom-based assessment is good. It is good for students to overcome his mistakes in writing

S4: I like most of the classroom-based assessment. Because it an assessment in which teacher helps student to write well.

S5: In my opinion classroom-based assessment is better to get feedback quickly.

S6: Classroom assessment is a good assessment for improving grammatical mistakes of drafts.

S7: I think so classroom-based assessment is a most effective for writing skills for papers.

S8: Classroom-based assessment is better for good writing.

S9: In my mind I prefer classroom-based assessment. It is fruitful for us.

S10: It is a good assessment which is classroom-based assessment. I mostly like it because in this technique we cover our mistakes.

S11: It is better to understand and appreciate classroom-based assessment.

S12: Classroom-based assessment is better for improving our writing skills rather than summative assessment.

S13: I would like to give to prefer classroom-based assessment because it a best tool for improvement of academic writing

S14: In my view Classroom-based Assessment is best.

S15: My view is that Classroom-based is good for writing skills. It is good technique.

S16: Mostly I prefer classroom-based assessment because it helpful in classroom to improve writing.

S17: What I think is that Classroom-based is best for writing.

S18: Classroom is best which mostly I prefer for motivation and for mistakes

S19: In my view Classroom-based assessment is better.

S20: I would like to prefer classroom-based assessment for correction of mistakes.

Table No # 02 Results of interview of second Question

Which assessment do you prefer to improve academic writing of the students?			
Theme / Node	Case	Percentage	References / Cases Response
Grammar Error	S1, S2, S3, S4, S8, S9, S13, S15, S16, S20	50	Sentence Structure, tenses and spelling.
Quick Feedback	S5, S7, S10, S14, S17, S18	30	Helps to get fast feedback
Pronunciation and Spelling	S6, S11, S12, S19	20	Words accent, pronunciation and fluency

It is stated that 50 % percent students were in favour of assessment for making writing better. 30% students favour to for better feedback 20 % percent for spelling correction.

From above all discussion it is described that main themes of this study explains that teacher can use different techniques in classroom to improve academic writing skills of the students. These techniques can be writing, listening and speaking. Most of the teachers showed a positive response for these techniques in classroom-based assessment. In semi structured interviews results showed that 70% percent teachers gave positive response related to writing technique in classroom-based assessment to improve writing skills of the undergraduate students. About 20 % percent people

also gave importance to summative assessment as well. Also, 10% percent of the students gave positive response to both formative and summative assessment.

Conclusion

Teachers and student's perception about CBA have indicated that in most cases it is beneficial because nowadays it is the best tool for assessing classroom-based assessment. Findings have indicated that CBA is most important techniques for improving students writing skills. Further, students and teacher's perception regarding classroom assessment was better. Further students' perceptions about the teacher's assistance and performance have depicted in the study that involves participate and assist students at SBBU,SBA. Student's perceptions over all about CBA have shown that it is the need of time and useful for every English language learner. In addition, it will prove productive for English language beginner.. Results have also shown that attitude of the teachers affects a lot for learning process of students. Positive attitude motivates students to participate actively in the while negative attitude demotivate students for language learning. The learners avoid attending the language class. The learners become slow in writing, speaking and reading English Consequently, leaner's meet with diverse complications in linguistic education and their weaknesses influence the future career as well.

The Future Recommendations

The findings of this study indicate that the classroom-based assessment for the English language is useful. It was very hard for the researcher to study the all dimensions the classroom-based assessment and focus was the general perceptions, the effectiveness of the classroom-based assessment in language learning, effecting factor for both teacher and students. Positive attitude motivates students to participate actively in the class while negative attitude demotivate students for language learning. The learners avoid attending the language class. The learners become slow in writing, speaking and reading English. Consequently, learners meet with diverse complications in linguistic education and their weakness influence the future career as well.

In addition, teacher co-operate students in group and individual as well. In addition, student's perception overall about classroom-based assessment have shown that it is need of the time and very useful for every English language learner. In addition, it will prove productive for English language for beginner. . Results have also shown that attitude of the teachers affect a lot of learning

process of the students. Positive attitude motivates students to participate actively in the class while negative attitude demotivate student for language learning. Thus, outcomes advocate the subsequent recommendations.

References

Ahmadi, N., Peter, L., Lubart, T., & Besançon, M. (2019). School Environments: Friend or Foe for Creativity Education and Research? In *Creativity under Duress in Education?* (pp. 255-266). Springer, Cham. argumentative essays. *Written Communication*, 28(1), 70-96. argumentative essays. *Written Communication*, 28(1), 70-96.

Auerbach, A. J. J., & Andrews, T. C. (2018). Pedagogical knowledge for active-learning instruction in large undergraduate biology courses: a large-scale qualitative investigation of instructor thinking. *International Journal of STEM Education*, 5(1). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10459-015-9652-7>

Abosalem, Y. (2016). Assessment techniques and students' higher-order thinking skills International Journal of Secondary Education, 4(1), 1-11. achievement in an urban elementary school. *The Reading Teacher*, 61(1), 32-43.

Becket, A. (2011). Student-generated scoring rubrics: Examining their formative value for improving ESL students' writing performance. *Assessing Writing*, 29, 15-24. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asw.2016.05.002>

Cresswell, T. (2013). *Place: A short introduction*. John Wiley & Sons.

-Donoso, R., & González, C. (2019). Undergraduate Research or Research-Based Physics: Conference Series (Vol. 1233, No. 1, p. 012093). IOP Publishing Practical Assessment, Research, and Evaluation, 7(1), 13. protest. *American sociological review*, 581-6

Durlak, J. A., Weissberg, R. P., Dymnicki, A. B., Taylor, R. D., & Schellinger, K. B. (2011). The impact of enhancing students' social and emotional learning: A meta-analysis of school-based universal interventions. *Child development*, 82(1), 405-432.

Earl, J., Soule, S. A., & McCarthy, J. D. (2003). Protest under fire? Explaining the policing of Education, 49(1), 91-107. *Education: handbook of English language teaching* (pp. 719-731). Springer, Education: Principles, Policy & Practice, 25(6), 551-575. children with CP. *Developmental Medicine & Child Neurology*, 50(9), 690-695.

Fisher, D., & Frey, N. (2007). Implementing a schoolwide literacy framework: Improving achievement in an urban elementary school. *The Reading Teacher*, 61(1), 32-43.

Kilgour, J. M., & Tayyaba, S. (2016). An investigation into the optimal number of distractors in single-best answer exams. *Advances in Health Sciences Education*, 21(3), 571-585. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10459-015-9652-7>

Obradović, J., Sulik, M. J., Finch, J. E., & Tirado-Strayer, N. (2018). Assessing students' of school-based universal interventions. *Child development*, 82(1), 405-432.

Rahmat, Y. P., Wilujeng, I., & Widowati, A. (2019, June). Reflective Thinking Profile for Junior High School Students in Service Learning-based Science. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* (Vol. 1233, No. 1, p. 012093).

Rincon-Flores, E. G., Gallardo, K., & de la Fuente, J. M. (2018). Strengthening an Educational Innovation Strategy: Processes to Improve Gamification in Calculus Course through Performance Assessment and Meta-Evaluation. *International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education*, 13(1), 1-11

Rustam, A., & Ramlan, A. M. (2017). Analysis of mathematical communication skills of Junior High School students of coastal Kolaka. *Journal of Mathematics Education*, 2(2), 45-51.

Yang, D., & Mak, C. M. (2017). An assessment model of classroom acoustical environment based on fuzzy comprehensive evaluation method. *Applied acoustics*, 127, 292-296.

Zhao, X., Van den Heuvel-Panhuizen, M., & Veldhuis, M. (2016). Teachers' use of classroom assessment techniques in primary mathematics education—an explorative study with six Chinese teachers. *International Journal of STEM Education*, 3(1), 19.

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Dedication

I dedicate this my research paper to my parents who are always behind my every success.

Conflicts of Interest

This is my original work and there is no conflict of interest

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